

ACCURATE ALIGNMENT SYSTEM FOR PHOTONIC BASED BIOSENSOR CARTRIDGES

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ABSTRACT

Photonic biosensors for medical diagnostics have been in development for some time. They have proven to show equal or better performance as compared to other techniques in terms of sensitivity, accuracy, and reliability [1]. In order for companies to successfully introduce these sensor products on the market, they must also perform equal or better in price per test and usability.

The price per test is to a large extent determined by the costs of the (disposable) cartridge containing the sensor chip and bioactive layer. If the active components can be left out of the cartridge a significant cost reduction can be obtained. However, this adds the challenge of coupling light from the source to the sensor chip inside the cartridge and back onto detectors.

This coupling requires a positioning accuracy in the (sub-) micrometer regime [2]. Here, we present a demonstrator system, which implements a passive alignment step followed by an active alignment procedure. The initial alignment is realized with high accuracy when placing a cartridge in an acceptor slot. This results in finding a “first light” state, which allows the active alignment to take over. Active alignment is then realized by moving the fiber by means of a set of actuators to the position with optimal coupling efficiency.

A demonstrator was designed and manufactured to test the influence of several key parameters, such as the influence of production accuracy of the cartridges on the initial alignment. The resulting system has shown to comply with the requirements of ease of alignment along with full automation.

KEYWORDS: photonics, cartridges, passive alignment, active alignment, demonstrator

INTRODUCTION

For photonic biosensors to be used in medical testing, they have to compete with existing technologies. These technologies and the logistics around them are highly optimized and automated. The important metrics for these optimizations are selectivity, sensitivity, price and usability. In discussion with end users it was found that in order for photonic biosensors to compete with these technologies, they will have to be at least equal or better at these metrics.

Sensitivity and selectivity are mostly depending on the bioactive layer whereas price and usability depend on the design of the measurement system. Such a measurement system for photonic biosensors includes one or more photonic integrated chips (PICs), optical active components such as laser(s) and photodiode(s), readout electronics and possibly some microfluidics for sample preparation and delivery.

In medical testing the components contacting patient samples are to be discarded as medical waste. Reducing the components to be discarded is therefore key to reducing the cost per test. A design where the test is split between a readout unit with the active components and electronics on one side and cartridges with the PIC and microfluidics on the other side reduces the medical waste and lowers the cost per test. It does, however, introduce the necessity to interface between the cartridge and the readout unit. According to the end users the signal to noise ratio (SNR) should be better than 25dB for test to be reliable.

A new design concept for the alignment between cartridges on one hand and active components inside the readout unit on the other is presented along with a performance test.

Figure 1: Initial demonstrator setup. Yellow the cartridge, black the active alignment, grey the passive alignment. Not shown the computerized control system.

CONCEPT

A simple photonic POC system consists of three parts: the cartridge, the readout unit and the software. Our concept assumes a two-step approach to the alignment of the PIC inside the cartridge and the components inside the readout unit. The first step is the insertion of the cartridge in an acceptor slot which is part of the readout unit.

This first step is used to bring the system in a “first light” state such that the second stage of the alignment can start. The second stage of alignment is the movement of the input fiber to achieve optimal coupling into the PIC. Output is collected at a 90 degree angle to minimize stray light at the detectors.

A demonstrator was part of the project to test several key parameters and production technologies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The demonstrator was used for rapid testing of different alignment solutions (Figure 1). The passive alignment between the different cartridge/acceptor concepts was tested for repeatability of the insertion of the cartridges and the influence of the cartridge production method.

Next to that, a highly accurate and fast three-axis alignment system which can be programmed to simulate different alternative actuation solutions. This system is controlled by a computer-controlled electronics, where variations in step sizes and coupled axes can be simulated, and their effect on coupling efficiency for different approach algorithms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Testing of the re-insertion accuracy of several cartridges was done. As can be seen from Figure 2 the accuracy is highly dependent on the production technology used.

For commissioning and operational testing a simple experiment was designed to align the focused output of an optical fiber with a waveguide using different alignment algorithms.

In Figure 3 the results of seven such experiments are shown. As can be seen the combination of the selected actuation system, the repositioning accuracy of the cartridge and the chosen alignment algorithm results in a >60dB SNR after 20 steps.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results, it is shown that the proposed combination of passive and active alignment allows for accurate coupling with a more than sufficient SNR. The time needed for alignment is well within the limits of the requirements.

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Figure 2: Comparison of the re-insertion accuracy of cartridges produced with different techniques. Series 1: standard FDM, 2: SLA, 3: high accuracy FDM.

Figure 3: Signal to Noise progression while testing two different alignment algorithms.